

Photochemical Formation of Peptides in Aqueous Solution of Glutamic Acid in Presence of Different Catalysts

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Sterilised aqueous solutions of glutamic acid after irradiation to sunlight for 400 hours, separately and also along with some of the catalysts of inorganic and organic origin, reveal by a two-way paper chromatographic technique the presence of several peptide spots along with a few amino-acids. Constituent amino-acids of the peptides have been observed by the same chromatographic technique after hydrolysing the irradiated mixtures. The dark solutions, covered with thick black cloth and equally irradiated, also furnish some of the peptides and amino-acids due to the influence of other radiations including the cosmic one.

Photochemical formation of amino-acids was reported by Bahadur and co-workers¹⁻³ when an aqueous mixture of paraformaldehyde, an inorganic source of nitrogen, and metallic ions as catalysts was exposed to sunlight or artificial light of an electric lamp. This work was further extended and the influences of pH and different sources of carbon and metallic catalysts⁴ were studied on photochemical formation of amino-acids⁵. The synthesis of amino-acids involving the fixation of molecular nitrogen was also reported⁶⁻⁹ when the aqueous mixtures of organic compounds and metallic ions were exposed to sunlight or artificial light.

Perti *et al.*¹⁰⁻¹⁵ have synthesised peptides photochemically by exposing the sterilised aqueous solutions of amino-acids containing sugar and metallic catalysts to sunlight and artificial light. Fox's thermal synthesis of peptides¹⁶ by heating aqueous mixtures of amino-acids to 170° is also noteworthy.

Bahadur¹⁷ has already stressed, on these lines, the formation of proteins or at least peptide-like material in prebiological era, which on further molecular evolution formed

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proteins; the theory regarding the origin of life on the Earth has been developed recently¹⁸⁻¹⁹.

In the present communication, the influence of some of the inorganic and organic catalysts on the photolysis of glutamic acid in aqueous solution and photochemical formation of peptides has been reported.

EXPERIMENTAL

The following nine sets, each of two Sigcol conical flasks of 150 ml capacity, were prepared. Each flask contained 100 ml solution in redistilled water. Glutamic acid used in the following sets was chromatographically pure.

- (a) 0.05% Glutamic acid.
- (b) 0.05% Glutamic acid + 0.02% ferrous sulphate (A.R.).
- (c) 0.05% Glutamic acid + 0.02% nickel sulphate (A.R.).
- (d) 0.05% Glutamic acid + 0.02% cobalt sulphate (A.R.).
- (e) 0.05% Glutamic acid + 0.02% molybdic acid (prepared from the interaction of A. R. potassium molybdate with A.R. HCl).
- (f) 0.05% Glutamic acid + 0.02% pure anthracene.
- (g) 0.05% Glutamic acid + 0.02% pure phenanthrene.
- (h) 0.05% Glutamic acid + 0.02% pure naphthalene.
- (i) 0.05% Glutamic acid + 0.02% pure fluorene.

The flasks were plugged with surgical cotton and sterilised at 15 lbs. pressure for 30 minutes. The mouths of the flasks were wrapped with polythene paper and sealed with cello-adhesive tape. One flask of each set was covered with thick black cloth and the other remained as such. All the covered and uncovered flasks were exposed to sunlight. After an exposure for 400 hr., the solutions of the covered and uncovered flasks were examined under the oil immersion microscope (D. R. P. Leitz Wetzlar microscope) using aseptic conditions and no bacterial growth was observed. The sterility of the exposed solutions was also checked by the culture-count method. A few drops of the exposed solution to be tested were introduced over the agar nutrient in the petri dishes under aseptic conditions and kept at 35° in the incubator for 3 to 4 days. The solutions did not show any bacterial growth during the exposure. These were analysed for hydrolysed and non-hydrolysed nitrogenous constituents by the two-way paper chromatographic technique, employing phenol-water (80:20) and butanol-acetic acid-water (120:30:50) as two running solvents. Hydrolysis was done with 10*N*-HCl in sealed, hard neutral glass ampules, kept in boiling water for 24 hr. The hydrolysed samples were dried and neutralised simultaneously in a vacuum desiccator in presence of

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fused NaOH. Whatman No. 1 chromatographic papers were used. Spots of amino-acids and peptides were developed by spraying 0.2% ninhydrin solution in acetone over the dried chromatograms. The R_f values changed due to many factors, such as change of room temperature²¹, the change of the time of running of the chromatograms in a particular solvent, and also due to the degree of hydration of the same solvent. Therefore the R_f values of known amino-acids were occasionally determined and the R_f values of unknown amino-acids were compared with these known ones. Two running solvents were used in all the experiments for identification. This was accompanied with two-dimensional chromatography.

The final identification was done by simultaneous running of known amino-acids with the running solvents used in these experiments. The results of the chromatographic analysis of each set are recorded in Tables I-IX, when time of exposure=400 hr.

TABLE I

Glutamic acid solution in water.

Conc. of glutamic acid=0.05%.

S. No.	R_f values in		*Identification.	Remarks.
	Phenol; water (80:20).	Butanol-acetic acid- water (120:30:50).		
A. Solution of uncovered flask (light).				
Unhydrolysed:				
1.	0.33	0.20	Peptide	Purple
2.	0.68	0.60	Peptide	Purple, faint
Hydrolysed:				
1.	0.10	0.37	Aspartic acid	Purple
2.	0.23	0.42	Glutamic acid	"
3.	0.32	0.36	Serine	"
4.	0.84	0.71	Norleucine	"
5.	0.94	0.77	?	Purple, faint
B. Solution of covered flask (dark).				
Unhydrolysed:				
1.	0.07	0.21	Peptide	Purple
2.	0.21	0.21	Peptide	"
3.	0.38	0.21	Glutamic acid?	"
4.	0.81	0.62	Peptide	"
Hydrolysed:				
1.	0.05	0.27	?	Pink
2.	0.00	0.36	?	"
3.	0.23	0.37	Glutamic acid	Purple
4.	0.84	0.71	Norleucine	Purple, faint

*With 0.2% ninhydrin solution in acetone.

TABLE II

Aqueous glutamic acid solution (0.05%) + ferrous sulphate (0.02%) as catalyst.

S.No.	R_f values in		Identification.	Remarks.
	Phenol-water (80:20).	Butanol-acetic acid-water (120:30:50).		
A. Solution of uncovered flask.				
Unhydrolysed:				
1.	0.17	0.23	Peptide	Purple, faint
2.	0.32	0.29	Glutamic acid	Purple
3.	0.45	0.23	Glycine	"
4.	0.75	0.50	?	"
5.	0.91	0.63	Peptide	"
Hydrolysed:				
1.	0.05	0.29	?	"
2.	0.32	0.23	Glycine	"
3.	0.30	0.29	Glutamic acid	"
4.	0.72	0.46	Alanine?	"
5.	0.62	0.78	?	"
B. Solution of covered flask.				
Unhydrolysed:				
1.	0.05	0.31	Peptide	Purple
2.	0.13	0.31	Aspartic acid	"
3.	0.32	0.30	Glutamic acid	"
4.	0.71	0.71	Peptide	"
Hydrolysed:				
1.	0.05	0.11	?	Purple, faint
2.	0.06	0.22	?	Red
3.	0.05	0.31	?	Purple
4.	0.12	0.30	Aspartic acid	"
5.	0.25	0.38	Glutamic acid	"
6.	0.40	0.28	Glycine	"
7.	0.90	0.70	Norleucine	"
8.	0.95	0.73	?	"

TABLE III

Aqueous solution of glutamic acid (0.05%) + nickel sulphate (0.02%) as catalyst.

S.No.	R_f values in		Identification.	Remarks.
	Phenol-water (80:20).	Butanol-acetic acid- water (120:30:50).		
A. Solution of uncovered flask.				
Unhydrolysed:				
1.	0.05	0.20	Peptide	Red
2.	0.15	0.20	Peptide	Purple
3.	0.37	0.20	Peptide	Purple
4.	0.78	0.60	Peptide	Brown
Hydrolysed:				
1.	0.10	0.40	Aspartic acid	Purple
2.	0.20	0.42	Glutamic acid	"
3.	0.35	0.36	Serine	"
4.	0.87	0.75	?	"
5.	0.97	0.68	Methionine	"

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TABLE III (contd.)

S. No.	R _f values in		Identification.	Remarks.
	Phenol-water (80:20).	Butanol-acetic acid water (120:30:50).		
B. Solution of covered flask.				
Unhydrolysed:				
1.	0.14	0.20	?	Red
2.	0.38	0.20	Peptide	Purple
Hydrolysed:				
1.	0.05	0.43	?	Red
2.	0.10	0.43	Aspartic acid	Purple
3.	0.37	0.40	Glutamic acid	"
4.	0.70	0.38	?	Purple, faint
5.	0.77	0.77	Tryptophane ?	Purple
6.	0.85	0.77	?	"
7.	0.90	0.80	Leucine	"

TABLE IV

Aqueous solution of glutamic acid (0.05%) + cobalt sulphate (0.02%) as catalyst.

S.No.	R _f values in		Identification.	Remark.
	Phenol-water (80:20).	Butanol-acetic acid- water (120:30:50).		
A. Solution of uncovered flask.				
Unhydrolysed:				
1.	0.05	0.21	?	Red
2.	0.14	0.21	Aspartic acid	Purple
3.	0.37	0.21	Peptide	"
4.	0.86	0.29	Peptide	"
5.	0.81	0.60	Peptide	"
Hydrolysed:				
1.	0.10	0.36	Aspartic acid	"
2.	0.21	0.42	Serine	"
3.	0.37	0.34	Glutamic acid	"
4.	0.87	0.72	Norleucine	"
B. Solution of covered flask				
Unhydrolysed:				
1.	0.06	0.20	?	Red
2.	0.14	0.20	Aspartic acid	Purple
3.	0.34	0.20	Peptide	"
4.	0.71	0.60	Peptide	Purple, faint
Hydrolysed:				
1.	0.10	0.36	Aspartic acid	Purple
2.	0.21	0.42	Glutamic acid	"
3.	0.37	0.37	Serine	"
4.	0.90	0.72	Norleucine	"

TABLE V

Aqueous glutamic acid solution (0.05%) + molybdc acid (0.02%) as catalyst.

S. No.	R _F values in		Identification.	Remarks.
	Phenol-water (80:20).	Butanol-acetic-acid- water (120:30:50).		
A. Solution of uncovered flask.				
Unhydrolysed:				
1.	0.15	0.23	?	Purple, faint
2.	0.15	0.30	Peptide	Purple
3.	0.37	0.30	Glutamic acid	"
4.	0.56	0.25	Peptide	"
5.	0.81	0.69	Peptide	"
Hydrolysed:				
1.	0.20	0.44	?	"
2.	0.27	0.42	Glutamic acid	"
3.	0.46	0.43	Threonine	"
4.	0.56	0.50	?	Very faint
B. Solution of covered flask.				
Unhydrolysed:				
1.	0.10	0.30	Peptide	Faint
2.	0.32	0.30	Glutamic acid	Deep purple
3.	0.75	0.68	Peptide	Brown
Hydrolysed:				
1.	0.05	0.44	?	Purple
2.	0.20	0.46	?	"
3.	0.27	0.43	Serine?	"
4.	0.32	0.45	Glutamic acid	"
5.	0.82	0.80	Norleucine	"

TABLE VI

Aqueous glutamic acid solution (0.05%) + anthracene (0.05%) as catalyst.

S.No.	R _F values in		Identification.	Remarks.
	Phenol-water (80:20).	Butanol-acetic acid- water (120:30:50).		
A. Solution of uncovered flask.				
Unhydrolysed:				
1.	0.17	0.15	Aspartic acid	Purple
2.	0.37	0.20	Peptide	"
3.	0.62	0.20	Histidine	"
4.	0.86	0.37	Peptide	"
5.	0.55	0.77	?	"
Hydrolysed:				
1.	0.05	0.22	?	Pink
2.	0.00	0.26	?	"
3.	0.12	0.21	Ornithine	Purple
4.	0.16	0.31	Aspartic acid	"
5.	0.25	0.36	Serine?	"
6.	0.37	0.30	Glutamic acid	"
7.	0.60	0.27	Histidine?	"
8.	0.77	0.47	?	"
9.	0.87	0.75	Norleucine	"
10.	0.60	0.78	?	"

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TABLE VI (contd.)

S. No.	R _f values in		Identification.	Remarks.
	Phenol-water (80:20).	Butanol-acetic acid- water (120:30:50).		
B. Solution of covered flask				
Unhydrolysed:				
1.	0.08	0.20	Peptide	Purple
2.	0.21	0.20	Peptide	"
3.	0.36	0.20	Glutamic acid	"
4.	0.41	0.20	Peptide	"
5.	0.77	0.62	Peptide	"
Hydrolysed:				
1.	0.05	0.27	?	Faint
2.	0.12	0.29	Aspartic acid	Faint purple
3.	0.25	0.36	Serine	Purple
4.	0.38	0.28	Glutamic acid	"
5.	0.85	0.57	?	Faint Purple
6.	0.92	0.60	?	"

TABLE VII

Aqueous glutamic acid solution (0.05%) + phenanthrene (0.02%) as catalyst.

S.No.	R _f values in		Identification.	Remark.
	Phenol-water (80:20).	Butanol-acetic acid- water (120:30:50).		
A. Solution of uncovered flask.				
Unhydrolysed:				
1.	0.17	0.21	Peptide	Purple
2.	0.40	0.21	Glutamic acid	"
3.	0.65	0.16	Peptide	"
4.	0.82	0.27	Peptide	Brown
5.	0.38	0.32	Peptide	"
6.	0.77	0.60	Peptide	"
Hydrolysed:				
1.	0.07	0.45	?	Faint
2.	0.22	0.53	?	Purple
3.	0.35	0.41	Glutamic acid	"
4.	0.81	0.53	?	"
5.	0.92	0.72	Phenylalanine	"
B. Solution of covered flask.				
Unhydrolysed:				
1.	0.08	0.20	Peptide	Faint
2.	0.23	0.20	Peptide	Purple
3.	0.40	0.20	Glutamic acid	"
4.	0.37	0.30	Peptide	Brown
5.	0.80	0.30	Peptide	"
6.	0.80	0.61	Peptide	Purple
Hydrolysed:				
1.	0.10	0.40	Aspartic acid	"
2.	0.25	0.47	Serine ?	"
3.	0.35	0.40	Glutamic acid	"
4.	0.92	0.74	Norleucine ?	"

TABLE VIII

Aqueous glutamic acid solution (0.05%) + naphthalene (0.02%) as catalyst.

S.No.	R _f values in		Identification.	Remarks.
	Phenol-water (80:20).	Butanol-acetic acid- water (120:30:50).		
S. Solution of uncovered flask.				
Unhydrolysed:				
1.	0.23	0.30	Peptide	Purple
2.	0.41	0.30	Glutamic acid	"
3.	0.42	0.35	Peptide	Brown
4.	0.61	0.26	Peptide	Purple
5.	0.82	0.36	Peptide	"
6.	0.82	0.67	Norleucine	"
7.	0.52	0.84	?	Faint
Hydrolysed:				
1.	0.05	0.41	?	Faint
2.	0.12	0.38	Aspartic acid	Purple
3.	0.20	0.44	Serine	"
4.	0.35	0.38	Glutamic acid	"
5.	0.92	0.70	Norleucine	"
B. Solution of covered flask.				
Unhydrolysed:				
1.	0.08	0.32	Peptide?	Pink
2.	0.20	0.32	Aspartic acid	Purple
3.	0.37	0.31	Glutamic acid	"
4.	0.78	0.36	Peptide	Yellow
5.	0.77	0.70	Norleucine	Purple
Hydrolysed:				
1.	0.05	0.38	?	Faint purple
2.	0.21	0.38	Aspartic acid	" "
3.	0.22	0.44	Serine	Purple
4.	0.35	0.37	Glutamic acid	"
5.	0.60	0.35	Alanine	Faint
6.	0.90	0.70	Norleucine	"
7.	0.95	0.75	Phenylalanine	Faint purple

TABLE IX

Aqueous glutamic acid solution (0.05%) + fluorene (0.02%) as catalyst.

S.No.	R _f values in		Identification.	Remark.
	Phenol-water (80:20).	Butanol-acetic acid- water (120:30:50).		
A. Solution of uncovered flask.				
Unhydrolysed:				
1.	0.11	0.29	Aspartic acid	Purple
2.	0.23	0.31	Peptide	"
3.	0.41	0.31	Glutamic acid	"
4.	0.41	0.40	Peptide	Brown
5.	0.55	0.28	Peptide	Purple
6.	0.80	0.41	Peptide	Brown
7.	0.77	0.75	Peptide	Purple

TABLE IX (contd.)

S. No.	R _f values in		Identification.	Remarks.
	Phenol-water (80:20).	Butanol-acetic acid- water (120:30:50).		
A. Solution of uncovered flask.				
Hydrolysed:				
1.	0.10	0.43	Aspartic acid?	Faint
2.	0.22	0.44	Serine	Purple
3.	0.32	0.41	Glutamic acid	Purple
4.	0.87	0.66	Phenylalanine	"
5.	0.92	0.72	Norleucine	"
B. Solution of covered flask.				
Unhydrolysed:				
1.	0.09	0.31	?	Pink
2.	0.22	0.31	Peptide	Purple
3.	0.40	0.31	Glutamic acid	"
4.	0.77	0.71	Peptide	"
Hydrolysed:				
1.	0.05	0.41	?	Pink
2.	0.12	0.41	Aspartic acid	Faint
3.	0.25	0.44	Serine	Purple
4.	0.37	0.37	Glutamic acid	"
5.	0.80	0.55	?	Faint purple
6.	0.85	0.66	Phenylalanine	Purple
7.	0.92	0.72	Norleucine	"

DISCUSSION

When the unhydrolysed and hydrolysed samples of the exposed glutamic acid solutions with different catalysts were studied by the two-way paper chromatographic technique, the spots of the various photolytic products were observed. A few of the spots from the unhydrolysed samples were of the amino-acids and the rest of the spots were considered to be of the peptides as these disappeared from the hydrolysed samples of the same mixture. A few faint spots of the unhydrolysed as well as hydrolysed samples, however, remained unidentified. Generally it had been observed that there were a few spots in unhydrolysed samples, but the same samples on hydrolysis provided several spots, which revealed the constituent amino-acid of those peptides which did not appear over the papers of the unhydrolysed samples.

The solutions, covered with thick black cloth, also furnished peptide spots, but lesser in number than those of the uncovered solutions. It has been observed by Bahadur and co-workers²⁰ that the covered solutions, which were simultaneously exposed along with uncovered solutions to sunlight, revealed the synthesis of amino-acids involving the fixation of molecular nitrogen, but similar solutions kept in lead chamber remained unchanged. The fact that other radiations including the cosmic one, which penetrated through the thick black cloth in dark solutions, synthesised some of the amino-acids. In lead chamber, where all the radiations including the cosmic one were cut off, nothing could take place.

Glutamic acid solution without any catalyst afforded two peptide spots which on hydrolysis provided aspartic acid, glutamic acid, serine, and norleucine with an unidenti-

ed faint spot. A similar solution, kept in dark, furnished glutamic acid and two peptide spots. On hydrolysis, glutamic acid and norleucine with two unidentified spots were observed.

Glutamic acid solution with ferrous sulphate provided glutamic acid with two peptide spots and an unidentified spot. The solution on hydrolysis afforded glycine, alanine, and glutamic acid with two unidentified spots. A similar solution, kept in uncovered flask, furnished aspartic acid, glutamic acid, and two peptide spots. The solution on hydrolysis provided aspartic acid, glutamic acid, glycine, alanine, and four unidentified faint spots including a red one.

Glutamic acid solution with nickel sulphate provided four peptide spots including one brown and one red. The solution on hydrolysis afforded glutamic acid, aspartic acid, serine, and methionine with an unidentified spot. A similar solution, kept in covered flask, provided the peptide spot with an unidentified spot. The solution on hydrolysis furnished glutamic acid, aspartic acid, and leucine along with four unidentified spots including a red one.

Glutamic acid solution with cobalt sulphate provided aspartic acid, three peptide spots, and an unidentified red spot. The solution on hydrolysis afforded aspartic acid, serine, glutamic acid, and norleucine. A similar solution, kept in covered flask, furnished aspartic acid, two peptide spots, and an unidentified spot. The solution on hydrolysis provided aspartic acid, glutamic acid, serine, and norleucine.

Glutamic acid solution with molybdic acid furnished three peptide spots with glutamic acid and an unidentified spot. The solution on hydrolysis furnished glutamic acid, threonine, and two unidentified spots. A similar solution, kept in covered flask, provided glutamic acid with two peptide spots. On hydrolysis serine, glutamic acid, and norleucine with two unidentified spots were observed.

Glutamic acid solution with anthracene furnished aspartic acid, histidine, and two peptide spots with an unidentified spot. The solution on hydrolysis provided ornithine, aspartic acid, serine, glutamic acid, histidine, and norleucine with four unidentified spots including two pink ones. A similar solution, kept in covered flask, provided glutamic acid with four peptide spots and this solution on hydrolysis afforded aspartic acid, serine, and glutamic acid with three unidentified spots.

Glutamic acid solution with phenanthrene provided five spots for peptides along with glutamic acid. On hydrolysis, glutamic acid and phenylalanine with three unidentified spots were observed. A similar solution, kept in covered flask, provided glutamic acid with five peptide spots. The solution on hydrolysis afforded aspartic acid, serine, glutamic acid, and norleucine.

Glutamic acid solution with naphthalene afforded four peptide spots with glutamic acid and norleucine along with two unidentified faint spots. On hydrolysis, aspartic acid, serine, glutamic acid, and norleucine with two unidentified faint spots were observed. A similar solution, kept in covered flask, provided two peptide spots with aspartic acid, glutamic acid, and norleucine. This solution on hydrolysis furnished aspartic acid, serine, glutamic acid, alanine, norleucine, and phenylalanine with an unidentified faint spot.

Glutamic acid solution with fluorene furnished aspartic acid, glutamic acid, and four peptide spots. On hydrolysis, aspartic acid, serine, glutamic acid, phenylalanine, and nor-

leucine were observed. A similar solution, kept in covered flask, furnished two peptide spots with glutamic acid along with an unidentified pink spot. The solution on hydrolysis provided aspartic acid, serine, glutamic acid, phenylalanine, and norleucine with two unidentified spots including a pink one. It was also observed on the basis of the number of photolytic products that organic catalysts, e.g. anthracene, phenanthrene, naphthalene, and fluorene, had somewhat better influence over the photolysis of glutamic acid in comparison to those of inorganic catalysis, such as nickel sulphate, ferrous sulphate, cobalt sulphate, and molybdc acid.

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